

Figure S1. Downregulation of TrkB with short hairpin (sh)TrkB blocked the treadmill running (TR)-induced inhibition of age-related microglial activation and DAT reduction in the striatum and motor deficit of middle-aged mice. Mice that underwent 3 months of TR [TR(3Mo)] and three intrastriatal injections of shLacZ or shTrkB viruses. (A) Levels of full-length (FL)-TrkB. (B) Representative micrographs in the striata Bar = 20 μ m. (C) Quantitative results of Iba1+ signals area. (D) Levels of p-p65 in the striata. (E) Representative micrographs of DAT+ signals in the striata. (F) Quantitative results of DAT+ signals. (G) Latency to fall off the rotarod. *** $p < 0.001$ versus respective Sed group; # $p < 0.05$, ### $p < 0.001$ versus respective shLacZ group, two-way ANOVA, Bonferroni's post hoc test. Full-length blots are presented in Figure S2.

Figure S2. Full-length blots cropped for representative figures.

Table S1. Sample size

Panel	Groups	n
Figure 1B, C, D, F	3-month-old mice	6
	6-month-old mice	6
	9-month-old mice	5
	12-month-old mice	5
Figure 1G, H	6-month-old mice	8
	9-month-old mice	8
	12-month-old mice	8
Figure 1I	6-month-old mice	10
	9-month-old mice	10
	12-month-old mice	10
Figure 2G, H	Pearson correlation	22
Figure 3B, C, G, H	9 Mo	11
	Ctl	11
	Ibu	11
Figure 3D	9 Mo	8
	Ctl	8
	Ibu	8
Figure 3E	9 Mo	5
	Ctl	5
	Ibu	5
Figure 4C, D, F	Saline	6
	Ki20227	6
Figure 5B, C, H, J	9 Mo	11
	Sed	11
	TR(1Mo)	11
	TR(3Mo)	11
Figure 5D, E, F, K, L, M	9 Mo	8
	Sed	8
	TR(1Mo)	8
	TR(3Mo)	8
Figure 6B, C	Sed	8
	TR(1Mo)	8
	TR(3Mo)	8
Figure 6D, F, G, J, S1A, S1F	Sed-shLacZ	8
	TR-shLacZ	8
	Sed-shTrkB	8
	TR-shTrkB	8
Figure 6H, S1D	Sed-shLacZ	7
	TR-shLacZ	7
	Sed-shTrkB	7
	TR-shTrkB	7
Figure S1C	Sed-shLacZ	5
	TR-shLacZ	5
	Sed-shTrkB	5
	TR-shTrkB	5
Figure S1G	Sed-shLacZ	9
	TR-shLacZ	9
	Sed-shTrkB	9
	TR-shTrkB	9

Table S2. Details of statistics results**Statistics Methods and Results (part 1.)**

Panel	Statistics methods	Statistics Results
Figure 1B	one-way ANOVA	$F = 7.96$, degree of freedom (d.f.) 3/18, $p = 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	3 Mo vs. 6 Mo: n.s.; 3 Mo vs. 9 Mo: n.s.; 3 Mo vs. 12 Mo: $p = 0.006$
Figure 1C	one-way ANOVA	$F = 19.53$, d.f. 3/18, $p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	3 Mo vs. 6 Mo: n.s.; 3 Mo vs. 9 Mo: n.s.; 3 Mo vs. 12 Mo: $p < 0.001$
Figure 1D	one-way ANOVA	$F = 10.24$, d.f. 3/18, $p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	3 Mo vs. 6 Mo: n.s.; 3 Mo vs. 9 Mo: $p = 0.009$; 3 Mo vs. 12 Mo: $p < 0.001$
Figure 1F	one-way ANOVA	$F = 9.20$, d.f. 3/18, $p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	3 Mo vs. 6 Mo: n.s.; 3 Mo vs. 9 Mo: $p = 0.009$; 3 Mo vs. 12 Mo: $p < 0.001$
Figure 1G	one-way ANOVA	$F = 12.15$, d.f. 2/21, $p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	6 Mo vs. 9 Mo: $p = 0.006$; 6 Mo vs. 12 Mo: $p < 0.001$
Figure 1H	one-way ANOVA	$F = 31.53$, d.f. 2/21, $p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	6 Mo vs. 9 Mo: $p < 0.001$; 6 Mo vs. 12 Mo: $p < 0.001$
Figure 1I	one-way ANOVA	$F = 96.38$, d.f. 2/27, $p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	6 Mo vs. 9 Mo: $p = 0.025$; 6 Mo vs. 12 Mo: $p < 0.001$
Figure 2G	Pearson correlation	TH neuron number v.s. Iba1 areas, $r = -0.66$, $p < 0.007$
Figure 2H	Pearson correlation	TH neuron number v.s. Iba1 cell numbers, $r = -0.59$, $p = 0.004$
Figure 3B	unpaired two-tailed Student's <i>t</i> test	$t = 5.49$, d.f. = 20, $p < 0.001$
Figure 3C	unpaired two-tailed Student's <i>t</i> test	$t = 4.26$, d.f. = 20, $p < 0.001$
Figure 3D	unpaired two-tailed Student's <i>t</i> test	$t = 6.31$, d.f. = 14, $p < 0.001$
Figure 3E	unpaired two-tailed Student's <i>t</i> test	$t = 2.43$, d.f. = 8, $p = 0.041$
Figure 3G	unpaired two-tailed Student's <i>t</i> test	$t = 5.70$, d.f. = 20, $p < 0.001$
Figure 3H	unpaired two-tailed Student's <i>t</i> test	$t = 2.98$, d.f. = 20, $p = 0.007$
Figure 4C	paired two-tailed Student's <i>t</i> test	$t = 4.14$, d.f. = 5, $p = 0.009$
Figure 4D	paired two-tailed Student's <i>t</i> test	$t = 5.01$, d.f. = 5, $p = 0.004$
Figure 4F	paired two-tailed Student's <i>t</i> test	$t = 3.18$, d.f. = 5, $p = 0.025$
Figure 5B	one-way ANOVA	$F = 32.87$, d.f. 2/30, $p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Sed vs. TR(1Mo): n.s.; Sed vs. TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$
Figure 5C	one-way ANOVA	$F = 41.68$, d.f. 2/30, $p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Sed vs. TR(1Mo): n.s.; Sed vs. TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$
Figure 5D	one-way ANOVA	$F = 7.48$, d.f. 2/21, $p = 0.004$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Sed vs. TR(1Mo): n.s.; Sed vs. TR(3Mo): $p = 0.003$
Figure 5E	one-way ANOVA	$F = 12.12$, d.f. 2/21, $p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Sed vs. TR(1Mo): n.s.; Sed vs. TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$
Figure 5F	one-way ANOVA	$F = 3.47$, d.f. 2/21, $p = 0.050$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Sed vs. TR(1Mo): n.s.; Sed vs. TR(3Mo): $p = 0.032$

Statistics Methods and Results (part 2.)		
Panel	Statistics methods	Statistics Results
Figure 5H	one-way ANOVA	$F = 52.39, d.f. 2/30, p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Sed vs. TR(1Mo): n.s.; Sed vs. TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$
Figure 5J	one-way ANOVA	$F = 24.13, d.f. 2/30, p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Sed vs. TR(1Mo): $p = 0.004$; Sed vs. TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$
Figure 5K	one-way ANOVA	$F = 25.66, d.f. 2/21, p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Sed vs. TR(1Mo): $p < 0.001$; Sed vs. TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$
Figure 5L	one-way ANOVA	$F = 5.06, d.f. 2/21, p = 0.016$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Sed vs. TR(1Mo): n.s.; Sed vs. TR(3Mo): $p = 0.017$
Figure 5M	one-way ANOVA	$F = 12.52, d.f. 2/21, p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Sed vs. TR(1Mo): n.s.; Sed vs. TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$
Figure 6B	one-way ANOVA	$F = 8.70, d.f. 2/21, p = 0.002$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Sed vs. TR(1Mo): n.s.; Sed vs. TR(3Mo): $p = 0.002$
Figure 6C	one-way ANOVA	$F = 11.65, d.f. 2/21, p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Sed vs. TR(1Mo): $p = 0.036$; Sed vs. TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$
Figure 6D	ordinary two-way ANOVA	interaction: $F(1, 28) = 3.03, p = 0.093$ shLacZ vs. shTrkB: $F(1, 28) = 52.59, p < 0.001$ Sed vs. TR: $F(1, 28) = 18.83, p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	shLacZ-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-Sed: $p = 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shLacZ-Sed: $p = 0.003$; shTrkB-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shTrkB-TR(3Mo): n.s.
Figure 6F	ordinary two-way ANOVA	interaction: $F(1, 28) = 7.55, p = 0.010$ shLacZ vs. shTrkB: $F(1, 28) = 46.84, p < 0.001$ Sed vs. TR: $F(1, 28) = 31.22, p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	shLacZ-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-Sed: $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shLacZ-Sed: $p = 0.044$; shTrkB-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shTrkB-TR(3Mo): n.s.
Figure 6G	ordinary two-way ANOVA	interaction: $F(1, 28) = 7.02, p = 0.013$ shLacZ vs. shTrkB: $F(1, 28) = 35.27, p < 0.001$ Sed vs. TR: $F(1, 28) = 14.29, p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	shLacZ-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-Sed: $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shLacZ-Sed: n.s.; shTrkB-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shTrkB-TR(3Mo): n.s.
Figure 6H	ordinary two-way ANOVA	interaction: $F(1, 24) = 8.82, p = 0.007$ shLacZ vs. shTrkB: $F(1, 24) = 35.61, p < 0.001$ Sed vs. TR: $F(1, 24) = 18.00, p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	shLacZ-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-Sed: $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shLacZ-Sed: n.s.; shTrkB-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shTrkB-TR(3Mo): n.s.
Figure 6J	ordinary two-way ANOVA	interaction: $F(1, 28) = 8.08, p = 0.008$ shLacZ vs. shTrkB: $F(1, 28) = 45.62, p < 0.001$ Sed vs. TR: $F(1, 28) = 23.47, p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	shLacZ-Sed vs. shLacZ-TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$; shLacZ-Sed vs. shTrkB-Sed: n.s.; shLacZ-TR(3Mo) vs. shTrkB-TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shTrkB-TR(3Mo): n.s.

Statistics Methods and Results (part 3.)

Panel	Statistics methods	Statistics Results
Figure S1A	ordinary two-way ANOVA	interaction: $F(1, 28) = 9.96, p = 0.004$ shLacZ vs. shTrkB: $F(1, 28) = 106.82, p < 0.001$ Sed vs. TR: $F(1, 28) = 13.36, p = 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	shLacZ-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-Sed: $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shLacZ-Sed: $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shTrkB-TR(3Mo): n.s.
Figure S1C	ordinary two-way ANOVA	interaction: $F(1, 16) = 7.88, p = 0.013$ shLacZ vs. shTrkB: $F(1, 16) = 110.37, p < 0.001$ Sed vs. TR: $F(1, 16) = 19.81, p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	shLacZ-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-Sed: $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shLacZ-Sed: $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shTrkB-TR(3Mo): n.s.
Figure S1D	ordinary two-way ANOVA	interaction: $F(1, 24) = 1.88, p = 0.183$ shLacZ vs. shTrkB: $F(1, 24) = 148.40, p < 0.001$ Sed vs. TR: $F(1, 24) = 6.54, p = 0.017$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	shLacZ-Sed vs. shLacZ-TR(3Mo): $p = 0.0626$; shLacZ-Sed vs. shTrkB-Sed: $p < 0.001$; shLacZ-TR(3Mo) vs. shTrkB-TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shTrkB-TR(3Mo): n.s.
Figure S1F	ordinary two-way ANOVA	interaction: $F(1, 28) = 12.60, p = 0.001$ shLacZ vs. shTrkB: $F(1, 28) = 134.07, p < 0.001$ Sed vs. TR: $F(1, 28) = 23.42, p < 0.001$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	shLacZ-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-Sed: $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-Sed vs. shLacZ-Sed: $p < 0.001$; shTrkB-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-TR(3Mo): $p < 0.001$, shTrkB-TR(3Mo) vs. shTrkB-Sed: n.s.
Figure S1G	ordinary two-way ANOVA	interaction: $F(1, 32) = 0.27, p = 0.605$ shLacZ vs. shTrkB: $F(1, 32) = 12.65, p = 0.001$ Sed vs. TR: $F(1, 32) = 11.34, p = 0.002$
	Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	shLacZ-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-Sed: n.s.; shTrkB-Sed vs. shLacZ-Sed: n.s.; shTrkB-TR(3Mo) vs. shLacZ-TR(3Mo): $p = 0.042$, shTrkB-TR(3Mo) vs. shTrkB-Sed: n.s.